

A Python Package For Summarizing University Student Examination Performance

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1. ARTICLE INFO

2. ABSTRACT

Keywords: isgc(Intelligent Student Grade Calculator), Semester Grading Point Average(SGPA), Cumulative Grade Point Average(CGPA), The Islamia University Of Bahawalpur (IUB)

This paper presents a numerical Python-based approach for computing Grade Point Averages (GPA's) and Cumulative Grade Point Averages (CGPAs) to enhance academic evaluation processes. The proposed methodology integrates custom rounding functions, visualization techniques, and subject remark analysis, offering a comprehensive solution for the helping of educational institutions. The core of the approach lies in processing subject details per semester, computes GPA's, and aggregates statistics for CGPA calculation. Manipulating a predefined grading scale, the function assigns grade points and remarks based on student's performance in individual subjects, ensuring accuracy and alignment with institutional criteria. To provide actionable insights, the methodology incorporates visualization components. Semester-wise GPA's are visualized using line plots, offering a clear depiction of academic performance trends over time. Furthermore, count-plots are generated to analyze subject remarks distribution, enabling stakeholders to identify areas of improvement and assess overall student performance comprehensively. It facilitates efficient academic evaluation processes, empowering students and academic administrators with precise metrics, graphical representations, and actionable insights. This paper contributes to the academic community by introducing a practical tool that enhances the evaluation and decision-making processes in educational institutions. Future research directions may explore additional features and optimizations to further improve the proposed methodology's utility and effectiveness.

3. INTRODUCTION

The Islamia University Of Bahawalpur, located in South Punjab, Pakistan, is a prestigious public sector institution with a rich historical legacy. Established in 1925 by Nawab Sir Sadiq Muhammad Khan Abbasi-V as Jammia Abbasia [1], the university has evolved over the decades, eventually attaining its current status as The Islamia University Of Bahawalpur in 1975 [2]. With a diverse faculty of over 200 and a student population exceeding 61,000, it stands as a bastion of higher education in the region (IUB).

For academic excellence, universities employ various assessment metrics for student performance. Among these, Semester Grading Point Average (SGPA) and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) [3] play pivotal roles in evaluating students' academic progress. However, calculating these metrics

accurately can be challenging for students, often leading to confusion and uncertainty regarding their academic standing [4].

Traditional methods of computing SGPA and CGPA are manual and prone to errors, while relying only on machine learning models may not provide exact solutions that align with individual student needs [3], [4]. To address these challenges, a Python package named isgc has been developed specifically for students of The Islamia University Of Bahawalpur. This package aims to streamline the calculation process and provide accurate SGPA and CGPA predictions, offering a user-friendly solution that eliminates the need for complex manual computations or generic machine learning models [5].

This paper presents a comprehensive overview of the development and implementation of the isgc package. An algorithmic design derived from the university's official guidelines, ensuring transparency and adherence to academic standards. Additionally, showcase the functionality of the package through real-world use cases and experiments, validating its accuracy against actual student transcripts. Through rigorous testing and analysis, we demonstrate how the isgc package empowers students to manage their academic performance effectively and make informed

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decisions regarding their educational journey.

The remainder of the paper is designed or organized as follows: in Section 4, the most important and relevant parts of the isgc algorithm are presented and explained, detailing the academic steps finalized by the university for calculation. In Section 5, the implementation of the package is introduced, and its use cases are outlined. Additionally, a detailed explanation of the use case scenarios is provided to illustrate the practical application of the isgc package. Section 6 presents an analysis of experiments conducted using real transcript data, wherein the accuracy of the isgc package is validated by comparing its output with actual measures. Through these experiments, the reliability and effectiveness of the package in real-world scenarios are demonstrated. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings and insights obtained from the study. Additionally, the implications of the research are discussed, and directions for future work to further enhance the functionality and utility of the isgc package are suggested.

4. ISGC ALGORITHM

This section comprehensively presents the important elements of the isgc algorithm, which is formulated based on the guidelines established by the Islamia University of Bahawalpur (IUB) for the evaluation of student performance in terms of semester grading and cumulative grade point average (CGPA) calculation. It elucidates several critical aspects, including the standard duration of credit hours according to the course type, the grading system utilized by the university, fractional handling procedures for numerical values, and the step-by-step process involved in computing both the semester grade point average (SGPA) and the CGPA. Furthermore, it introduces a visualization method designed to illustrate the outcome of these calculations effectively. Through a detailed examination of these components, this section offers a comprehensive understanding of the isgc algorithm, facilitating accurate and transparent assessment of students' academic progress at the Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

A. Standard duration of credit hour

Algorithm 1 describes standard duration of credit hour. Data can be credit-hours and course-type. Result dependent on both these. For course type named **theory** and course type **practical** calculation explained. The standard duration of a credit hour is described in given table I:

Let $\mathcal{C} : \text{CreditHour} \times \text{Type} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a function defined as:

$$\mathcal{C}(c, \text{Theory}) \mapsto 16c$$

$$\mathcal{C}(c, \text{Practical}) \mapsto 32c \text{ to } 48c$$

where CreditHour represents the credit hours, Type represents the course type, and $\mathcal{C}(c, \text{Theory})$ and $\mathcal{C}(c, \text{Practical})$ represent the equivalent hours for theory and practical courses, respectively.

Algorithm 1: Calculate Equivalent Hours

Data: creditHours, courseType

Result: equivalentHours

- 1 **if** courseType is "Theory" **then**
 - 2 equivalentHours $\leftarrow$ creditHours $\times$ 16;
 - 3 **else if** courseType is "Practical" **then**
 - 4 equivalentHours $\leftarrow$ Random value in $[32 \times$
 creditHours, $48 \times$ creditHours];
 - 5 **return** equivalentHours;
-

TABLE I: Credit Hour Equivalents in a Semester

Type	Equivalent Hours
Theory	1 Credit Hour = 16 hours
Practical	1 Credit Hour = 32-48 hours

B. Grading

1) *Grade System Points-Grade*: The grading of students rated according to 4 Letter grade system given. For Example, **A, B, C and D** with **Nine** performance levels of **A⁺, A, B, C and D** For Master Degree. While, For these grades, **F** will be a failing grade. In given cases, n is equal to 100.

$$\text{Grade System Point}(n) = \begin{cases} A+ & \text{if } n \geq 95.0 \\ A & \text{if } 85.0 \leq n < 95.0 \\ B & \text{if } 70.0 \leq n < 85.0 \\ C & \text{if } 60.0 \leq n < 70.0 \\ D & \text{if } 50.0 \leq n < 60.0 \\ F & \text{if } n < 50.0 \end{cases}$$

2) *Grade System Point-Gradient Point*: : Gradient Point is the most important measure to ensure correct calculation. It also based on numeric equivalence.

$$\text{GSP}(n) = \begin{cases} A+, A & \text{if } 4.0, n \geq 85.0 \\ B & \text{if } 3.0 - 3.9, 70.0 \leq n < 85.0 \\ C & \text{if } 2.0 - 2.9, 60.0 \leq n < 70.0 \\ C & \text{if } 1.0 - 1.9, 50.0 \leq n < 60.0 \\ F & \text{if } 0.0, n < 50.0 \end{cases}$$

3) *Grade System Point-Main*: : In this section, a comprehensive grading point table II is presented, providing a detailed breakdown of grade points corresponding to numerical grades. This table serves as the basis for accurate calculation of grades and grade points.

Algorithm 2: Calculate Grade Based on Points

Data: points (n)
Result: grade

```

1 if  $points \geq 95.0$  then
2   | grade  $\leftarrow$  "A+";
3 else if  $85.0 \leq points < 95.0$  then
4   | grade  $\leftarrow$  "A";
5 else if  $70.0 \leq points < 85.0$  then
6   | grade  $\leftarrow$  "B";
7 else if  $60.0 \leq points < 70.0$  then
8   | grade  $\leftarrow$  "C";
9 else if  $50.0 \leq points < 60.0$  then
10  | grade  $\leftarrow$  "D";
11 else
12  | grade  $\leftarrow$  "F";
13 return grade;

```

Algorithm 3: Grade System Point Algorithm

Data: points (n)
Result: grade

```

1 if  $n \geq 85.0$  then
2   | grade  $\leftarrow$  "A+" or "A" with "4.0";
3 else
4   | if  $70.0 \leq n < 85.0$  then
5     | grade  $\leftarrow$  "B" with "3.0-3.9";
6   | else
7     | if  $60.0 \leq n < 70.0$  then
8       | grade  $\leftarrow$  "C" with "2.0-2.9";
9     | else
10      | if  $50.0 \leq n < 60.0$  then
11        | grade  $\leftarrow$  "D" with "1.0-1.9";
12      | else
13        | if  $n < 50.0$  then
14          | grade  $\leftarrow$  "F" with "0.0";
15        | else
16          | grade  $\leftarrow$  "Invalid Input";
17 return grade;

```

C. Fraction Handling

Fraction handling involves rounding up numerical values to the nearest whole number, as per the university's guidelines. The methodology for rounding fractional values is discussed, with examples provided to illustrate the process. In this set the rule for fraction values. For example, fraction marks 0.50 and above obtained in a course is to be rounded up to the next whole figure such as 74.50 to 75.00.

$$\text{Rounded value}(n) = \begin{cases} \lceil n \rceil & \text{if } n - \lfloor n \rfloor \geq 0.50 \\ \lfloor n \rfloor & \text{if } n - \lfloor n \rfloor < 0.50 \end{cases}$$

TABLE II: Grading System Table

Numeric Grade	Grade Point	Grade	Remark
100	4.0	A+	Excellent
99	4.0	A+	Excellent
98	4.0	A+	Excellent
97	4.0	A+	Excellent
96	4.0	A+	Excellent
95	4.0	A+	Excellent
94	4.0	A	Very Good
93	4.0	A	Very Good
92	4.0	A	Very Good
91	4.0	A	Very Good
90	4.0	A	Very Good
89	4.0	A	Very Good
88	4.0	A	Very Good
87	4.0	A	Very Good
86	4.0	A	Very Good
85	4.0	A	Very Good
84	3.9	B	Good
83	3.9	B	Good
82	3.8	B	Good
81	3.7	B	Good
80	3.7	B	Good
79	3.6	B	Good
78	3.5	B	Good
77	3.5	B	Good
76	3.4	B	Good
75	3.3	B	Good
74	3.3	B	Good
73	3.2	B	Good
72	3.1	B	Good
71	3.1	B	Good
70	3.0	B	Good
69	2.9	C	Satisfactory
68	2.8	C	Satisfactory
67	2.7	C	Satisfactory
66	2.6	C	Satisfactory
65	2.5	C	Satisfactory
64	2.4	C	Satisfactory
63	2.3	C	Satisfactory
62	2.2	C	Satisfactory
61	2.1	C	Satisfactory
60	2.0	C	Satisfactory
59	1.9	D	Poor
58	1.8	D	Poor
57	1.7	D	Poor
56	1.6	D	Poor
55	1.5	D	Poor
54	1.4	D	Poor
53	1.3	D	Poor
52	1.2	D	Poor
51	1.1	D	Poor
50	1.0	D	Poor
49	0.0	F	Fail

Here, n represents the numerical value. The formula checks the fractional part of n :

- If the fractional part is 0.50 or above, the formula rounds up using the **ceiling function** $\lceil \cdot \rceil$.
- If the fractional part is less than 0.50, the formula rounds down using the **floor function** $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$.

Example:

Suppose have a numerical value $n = 74.50$:

$$\text{value}(74.50) = \begin{cases} \lceil 74.50 \rceil & \text{if } 74.50 - \lfloor 74.50 \rfloor \geq 0.50 \\ \lfloor 74.50 \rfloor & \text{if } 74.50 - \lfloor 74.50 \rfloor < 0.50 \end{cases}$$

Since the fractional part (0.50) is equal to or above

0.50, apply the ceiling function:

$$\text{Rounded value}(74.50) = \lceil 74.50 \rceil = 75$$

Therefore, the rounded value for 74.50 is 75.

Example:

Suppose have a numerical value $n = 23.30$:

$$\text{value}(23.30) = \begin{cases} \lceil 23.30 \rceil & \text{if } 23.30 - \lfloor 23.30 \rfloor \geq 0.50 \\ \lfloor 23.30 \rfloor & \text{if } 23.30 - \lfloor 23.30 \rfloor < 0.50 \end{cases}$$

Since the fractional part (0.30) is less than 0.50, apply the floor function:

$$\text{Rounded value}(23.30) = \lfloor 23.30 \rfloor = 23$$

Therefore, the rounded value for 23.30 is 23.

D. SGPA Calculation

The SGPA (*Semester Grade Point Average*) of a student is calculated as follows:

$$\text{SGPA} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\text{Quality Points}_i \times \text{Credit Hours}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{Credit Hours}_i}$$

Here:

- n is the number of courses in the semester.
- Quality Points _{i} are the quality points corresponding to the grade obtained in the i -th course.
- Credit Hours _{i} are the credit hours of the i -th course.

Algorithm 4: Calculate SGPA

```

1: Input: Number of courses in the semester ( $n$ ).
2: Initialize:
3:   totalQualityPoints = 0
4:   totalCreditHours = 0 for  $i = 1$  to  $n$  do
5:
   Input: Quality Point for the  $i$ -th course
   (Quality Points $i$ ).
6: Input: Credit Hours for the  $i$ -th course
   (Credit Hours $i$ ).
7: Calculate: qualityPointsProduct =
   Quality Points $i$  × Credit Hours $i$ 
8: Update: totalQualityPoints =
   totalQualityPoints + qualityPointsProduct
9: Update: totalCreditHours =
   totalCreditHours + Credit Hours $i$ 
10:
11: Calculate: SGPA =  $\frac{\text{totalQualityPoints}}{\text{totalCreditHours}}$ 
12: Output: The calculated SGPA.

```

E. CGPA Calculation

After calculation of SGPA of n semesters, CGPA can be calculated by given formula:

$$\text{CGPA} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m (\text{SGPA}_j \times \text{Semester Credit Hours}_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^m \text{Semester Credit Hours}_j}$$

where:

- m is the number of semesters,
- SGPA _{j} is the SGPA of the j -th semester,
- Semester Credit Hours _{j} is the total credit hours for courses taken in the j -th semester.

Algorithm 5: Calculate CGPA

```

1: Input: Number of semesters ( $m$ ).
2: Initialize:
3:   totalQualityPoints = 0
4:   totalCreditHours = 0 for  $j = 1$  to  $m$  do
5:
   Input: SGPA for the  $j$ -th semester (SGPA $j$ ).
6: Input: Credit Hours for the  $j$ -th semester
   (Semester Credit Hours $j$ ).
7: Calculate: semesterQualityPoints =
   SGPA $j$  × Semester Credit Hours $j$ 
8: Update: totalQualityPoints =
   totalQualityPoints + semesterQualityPoints
9: Update: totalCreditHours =
   totalCreditHours + Semester Credit Hours $j$ 
10:
11: Calculate: CGPA =  $\frac{\text{totalQualityPoints}}{\text{totalCreditHours}}$ 
12: Output: The calculated CGPA.

```

F. Visualization Report

1) *Semester-Wise GPA:* This visualization illustrates the progression of Semester Grade Point Averages (SGPAs) across various semesters. Each data point on the line plot corresponds to the SGPA of a specific semester, with individual markers denoting these data points. Additionally, a red dashed line represents the Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) approximately. This visualization offers a clear overview of the student's academic performance throughout different semesters.

2) *Number of Subjects with Same Grade Remarks (All Semesters):* It visualizes the count plot showcasing the distribution of subjects with identical grade remarks across all semesters. Each bar on the plot represents the number of subjects sharing the same grade remarks. This visualization helps to identify patterns in the distribution of grades and provides insights into the frequency of specific grade remarks across different courses and semesters.

5. PACKAGE IMPLEMENTATION

This section provides insights into the implementation details of the isgc package, a Python-based tool designed to facilitate the computation of Semester Grade Point Averages (SGPAs) and Cumulative Grade Point Averages (CGPAs) for students enrolled at the Islamia University of Bahawalpur (IUB). The package, developed using Python, is hosted on the Python Package Index (PYPI)¹ and source code is publically available on (GitHub)² for convenient access.

The isgc package encompasses several key components:

- 1) **Algorithms:** The package incorporates algorithms compliant with IUB guidelines for calculating equivalent hours, grade points, SGPA, and CGPA. These algorithms are implemented as Python functions, forming the backbone of the package's computational capabilities.
- 2) **Data Structures:** The package utilizes appropriate data structures, such as dictionaries and lists, to manage and manipulate data related to courses, grades, credit hours, and other relevant information.
- 3) **Input Handling:** Input handling mechanisms are implemented to validate and process user-provided data accurately. This involves verifying the integrity of input data, such as course grades and credit hours, before initiating calculations.
- 4) **Output Formatting:** Upon completing calculations, the package formats the results into human-readable formats, such as text output, tabular form or graphical representations, to provide users with clear and concise information regarding their academic performance.
- 5) **Error Handling:** Comprehensive error handling mechanisms are integrated into the package to gracefully manage exceptional cases, including invalid input data or calculation errors. Informative error messages are provided to aid users in troubleshooting.
- 6) **Documentation and Usage Guidelines:** The package includes extensive documentation and usage guidelines to assist users in installing, importing, and effectively utilizing its functionalities.
- 7) **Testing and Validation:** Rigorous testing and validation procedures are conducted to verify the accuracy and reliability of the package. Unit tests are employed to validate individual functions, while integration tests assess the overall behavior of the package.

By adhering to these principles and best practices, the isgc package offers an efficient and user-friendly solution for IUB students to accurately compute their SGPA and CGPA without the need for manual calculations or external tools.

A. Custom Round Function

To ensure accuracy in rounding off numerical values, a custom rounding function is developed. The flowchart depicting the operation of this function is presented in Figure 1, followed by the algorithmic representation in Algorithm 6. The custom round function ensures accurate rounding of numerical values, which is crucial for maintaining precision in various calculations, such as GPA computation and result visualization.

Algorithm 6: Custom Round

Input: number, decimal_places

Output: rounded_number

- 1 custom_round (number, decimal_places)
factor $\leftarrow 10^{\text{decimal_places}}$;
 - 2 rounded_number $\leftarrow \frac{\text{int}(\text{number} \times \text{factor} + 0.5)}{\text{factor}}$;
 - 3 return rounded_number;
-

Fig. 1: Flowchart for the custom_round function

B. Display Name

To enhance the visual appeal and creativity, the display name function incorporates the use of the **pyfiglet** Python package, which generates ASCII banners. The operation of this function is illustrated in Algorithm 7 and the accompanying flowchart in Figure 2.

Algorithm 7: Display Name

Input: name

- 1 display_name (name) ascii_banner $\leftarrow$
pyfiglet.figlet_format(name);
 - 2 print(ascii_banner);
-

C. Semester Wise Overview Plot

The semester-wise overview plot provides a comprehensive visualization of the calculated measures across

Fig. 2: Flowchart for the display_name function

Fig. 3: Semester-wise GPA and CGPA Plot Flowchart

different semesters, offering valuable insights into the academic performance trends over time. This plot, depicted as a line graph, presents a clear and intuitive representation of the data. The algorithm outlined and the accompanying flowchart in Figure 3 describe the process of generating this plot in detail.

D. Remarks Subjects Overview Plot

In this, examine and show the countplot which describes total subjects remarks point of view. An algorithm 4 and flowchart 5 help us to understand the process.

Algorithm 9: Semester-wise GPA and CGPA Plot

Input: a, b, c

1 semester_wise_plot(a, b, c)

2

Fig. 4: Subject Remarks Count Algorithm

Fig. 5: Remark-wise subjects overview

E. Tabular View Of Calculations

In this, print out calculation of credit hours, semester-wise SGPA, quality points, rounded percentage, obtained marks, total marks. use a Python package **tabulate** for this process. It provides an attractive overview to display these measures. Here is an algorithm 10

Algorithm 10: Print Result Table

Input: result_table

```

1 result_table
2 print_table(result_table) // Define
  table headers
3 headers ← ['Semester', 'SGPA', 'Total CH',
  'Total %', 'Total TM', 'Total OM', 'Total
  QP'];
  // Print the table using
  tabulate
4 print(tabulate(result_table, headers=headers,
  tablefmt='fancy_grid'));
```

F. Complete Algorithm Steps:

1) Import necessary libraries:

- tabulate
- matplotlib.pyplot
- seaborn
- pyfiglet

2) Define display_name function:

- **Input:** name (string)
- **Output:** None
- Display the input name in ASCII art using pyfiglet.

3) Define custom_round function:

- **Input:** number (float), decimal_places (int)
- **Output:** Rounded number (float)
- Round the input number to the specified number of decimal places.

4) Define semester_wise_plot function:

- **Input:** a (list of semesters), b (list of SGPA values), c (CGPA value)
- **Output:** None

- Plot a line graph showing SGPA for each semester and a horizontal line for CGPA.

5) Define subject_remarks function:

- **Input:** a (list of grade remarks for each subject)
- **Output:** None
- Plot a count of subjects with the same grade remarks across all semesters.

6) Define calculate_gpa function:

- **Input:** semesters (dictionary containing subject details for each semester)
- **Output:** CGPA (float)
- Initialize grading_scale dictionary with grade points and remarks.
- Initialize variables for overall statistics.
- Loop through each semester:
 - Initialize variables for semester statistics.
 - Loop through each subject in the semester:
 - * Calculate percentage, grade point, remark, quality point.
 - * Update semester statistics and subject grade remarks.
 - Calculate semester GPA.
 - Update overall statistics.
 - Append semester statistics to result table.
- Calculate CGPA.
- Print semester-wise results using tabulate.
- Plot semester-wise GPA and subject grade remarks using defined functions.
- Display CGPA.
- Return CGPA.

7) Example Usage:

- Provide the details of subjects and grades for each semester in the form of a dictionary.
- Call the calculate_gpa function with the provided data.

G. Project Directory Structure:

The complete Project Directory Structure is given below:

```

isgc/
|-- build/
|   |-- bdist.linux-x86_64/
|   |-- lib/
|   |-- isgc/
|       |-- gpa_calculator/
|           |-- calculator.py
|           |-- count_plot_remarks.py
|           |-- custom_round.py
|           |-- display_name.py
|           |-- __init__.py
|           |-- semester_wise_sgpa_cgpa.py
|           |-- __init__.py
|-- dist/
|   |-- isgc-0.1.10-py3-none-any.whl
|   |-- isgc-0.1.10.tar.gz
|   |-- isgc-1.0.1-py3-none-any.whl
|   |-- isgc-1.0.1.tar.gz
|   |-- isgc-1.0.2-py3-none-any.whl
|   |-- isgc-1.0.2.tar.gz
|-- isgc/
|   |-- gpa_calculator/
|   |   |-- calculator.py
|   |   |-- __init__.py
|   |   |-- __init__.py
|   |-- __init__.py
|-- isgc.egg-info/
|   |-- dependency_links.txt
|   |-- entry_points.txt
|   |-- PKG-INFO
```

```

|-- requires.txt
|-- SOURCES.txt
|-- top_level.txt
|-- README.md
|-- setup.py
|-- tests/
|-- __init__.py
|-- test_calculator.py

```

H. Example Code:

Listing 1: CGPA Calculation Script

```

from isgc.gpa_calculator.calculator import calculate_gpa

semesters = {
    'Semester#1': {
        'Subject_1': {'credit_hours': 2, 'marks': 44, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_2': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 76, 'total_marks':100},
        'Subject_3': {'credit_hours': 2, 'marks': 36, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_4': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 46, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_5': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 31, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_6': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 43, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_7': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 88, 'total_marks':100},
        'Subject_8': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 44, 'total_marks':50},
    },
    'Semester#2': {
        'Subject_1': {'credit_hours': 2, 'marks': 44, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_2': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 76, 'total_marks':100},
        'Subject_3': {'credit_hours': 2, 'marks': 36, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_4': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 46, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_5': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 31, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_6': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 43, 'total_marks':50},
        'Subject_7': {'credit_hours': 3, 'marks': 160, 'total_marks':200},
        'Subject_8': {'credit_hours': 1, 'marks': 44, 'total_marks':50},
    },
}

cgpa = calculate_gpa(semesters)

print(f"CGPA:#{cgpa}")

```

6. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, experiments are conducted to rigorously evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the package in calculating semester-wise measures. The experiments involve analyzing the transcript data of a under-graduate from the Islamia University Bahawalpur (IUB) and comparing the calculated results with the expected outcomes.

A. Transcript Data

The transcript data of a randomly selected graduate from IUB is obtained. Two sample transcripts, denoted as 6 and 7:, are provided for analysis. The transcript data includes information about the courses taken in each semester, along with the corresponding grades and credit hours.

B. Installation

This section provides instructions for installing the 'isgc' module on any Python-compatible operating system. To install the module, follow the steps outlined below:

- 1) Open a terminal or command prompt on your system.
- 2) Use the following command to install the 'isgc' module using 'pip':

```
pip install isgc
```

This command will automatically download and install the module along with its dependencies from the Python Package Index (PyPI)⁸.

The Islamia University of Bahawalpur		Faculty of Engineering		B.Sc. Computer Systems Engineering		Session:2020-24			
Name: Ahsan Tariq		Provisional		Roll No. F20BCSEN1M01026		Registration No. Fall-2020-IU-967			
Father's Name: Tariq Mehmood									
Course Code	Course Name	Credit Hours	Marks Obtained/ Grade Points			G.P.A.	Letter Grade	Quality Points	
			Theory	G.P.	Practical				G.P.
Semester - I									
ISLA-00100	Islamic Studies	2+0	44	4.00		4.00	A	8.00	
MATH-00101	Calculus & Analytical Geometry	3+0	89	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
COMP-01102	Computer Fundamentals	2+1	39	3.50	46	4.00	B+	11.00	
ELEN-01103	Circuit Analysis	3+1	51	1.10	48	4.00	D	7.30	
ENGL-00104	Functional English	3+0	85	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
ELEN-01105	Workshop Practice	0+1			45	4.00	A	4.00	
						SGPA	3.39	CGPA	3.39
Semester - II									
MATH-00206	Linear Algebra	3+0	90	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
PAKS-00207	Pakistan Studies	2+0	43	4.00		4.00	A	8.00	
COMP-01208	Computer Programming	3+1	75	3.00	43	4.00	B	13.90	
ENGL-00209	Communication Skills	3+0	87	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
ELEC-01210	Electronic Devices and Circuits	3+1	77	3.50	50	4.00	B+	14.50	
						SGPA	3.78	CGPA	3.58
Semester - III									
MATH-00311	Complex Variables and Transforms	3+0	85	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
ELEN-01312	Digital Logic Design	3+1	90	4.00	46	4.00	A	16.00	
COMP-01313	Data Structures and Algorithms	3+1	90	4.00	46	4.00	A	16.00	
MATH-00314	Discrete Structures	3+0	69	2.90		2.90	C+	8.70	
COMP-01315	Computer Applications in Engineering	0+1			49	4.00	A+	4.00	
MGMT-03345	Entrepreneurship	3+0	77	3.50		3.50	B+	10.50	
TSQAQ-00301	Arabic For Understanding Quran	3+0	81	3.70		3.70	B+	11.10	
						SGPA	3.73	CGPA	3.64
Semester - IV									
MATH-00416	Differential Equations	3+0	88	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
COMP-01417	Object Oriented Programming	3+1	80	3.70	45	4.00	B+	15.10	
ELEN-01418	Signals & Systems	3+1	64	2.40	42	3.90	C+	11.10	
ENGL-00419	Technical Writing	2+0	45	4.00		4.00	A	8.00	
COMP-01420	Computer Architecture	2+1	34	2.80	48	4.00	C	9.60	
						SGPA	3.49	CGPA	3.61
Semester - V									
COMP-01523	Computer Communication Networks	3+1	68	2.80	47	4.00	B	12.40	
COMP-02524	Database Management Systems	3+1	53	1.30	48	4.00	D	7.90	
MATH-00525	Numerical Methods	2+1	40	3.70	40	3.70	B+	11.10	
ELEN-02522	Microprocessors & Interfacing	3+1	72	3.10	40	3.70	B	13.00	
MATH-00523	Probability Methods in Engineering	3+0	82	3.80		3.80	B+	11.40	
						SGPA	3.10	CGPA	3.50

Note: University reserves the right to correct errors & omissions if any.

Credit Hours:	87	Total Marks:	369
Cumulative Grade Point Average:	3.50	Obtained Marks:	3481
Grade:	B	Percentage:	78.38
Degree Status:	Incomplete		

Fig. 6: A sample Transcript 1

The Islamia University of Bahawalpur		Faculty of Engineering		B.Sc. Computer Systems Engineering		Session:2020-24			
Name: M. Usman Akram		Provisional		Roll No. F20BCSEN1M01014		Registration No. Fall-2020-IU-958			
Father's Name: Muhammad Akram									
Course Code	Course Name	Credit Hours	Marks Obtained/ Grade Points			G.P.A.	Letter Grade	Quality Points	
			Theory	G.P.	Practical				G.P.
Semester - I									
ISLA-00100	Islamic Studies	2+0	44	4.00		4.00	A	8.00	
MATH-00101	Calculus & Analytical Geometry	3+0	76	3.40		3.40	B	10.20	
COMP-01102	Computer Fundamentals	2+1	36	3.10	46	4.00	B	10.20	
ELEN-01103	Circuit Analysis	3+1	91	4.00	43	4.00	A	16.00	
ENGL-00104	Functional English	3+0	88	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
ELEN-01105	Workshop Practice	0+1			44	4.00	A	4.00	
						SGPA	3.78	CGPA	3.78
Semester - II									
MATH-00206	Linear Algebra	3+0	83	3.90		3.90	B+	11.70	
PAKS-00207	Pakistan Studies	2+0	38	3.40		3.40	B	6.80	
COMP-01208	Computer Programming	3+1	84	3.90	45	4.00	B+	15.70	
ENGL-00209	Communication Skills	3+0	67	2.70		2.70	C+	8.10	
ELEC-01210	Electronic Devices and Circuits	3+1	91	4.00	36	3.10	B+	15.10	
						SGPA	3.59	CGPA	3.68
Semester - III									
MATH-00311	Complex Variables and Transforms	3+0	73	3.20		3.20	B	9.60	
ELEN-01312	Digital Logic Design	3+1	90	4.00	45	4.00	A	16.00	
COMP-01313	Data Structures and Algorithms	3+1	94	4.00	47	4.00	A	16.00	
MATH-00314	Discrete Structures	3+0	70	3.00		3.00	B	9.00	
COMP-01315	Computer Applications in Engineering	0+1			49	4.00	A+	4.00	
MGMT-03345	Entrepreneurship	3+0	67	2.70		2.70	C+	8.10	
TSQAQ-00301	Arabic For Understanding Quran	3+0	90	4.00		4.00	A	12.00	
						SGPA	3.56	CGPA	3.63
Semester - IV									
MATH-00416	Differential Equations	3+0	71	3.10		3.10	B	9.30	
COMP-01417	Object Oriented Programming	3+1	85	4.00	46	4.00	A	16.00	
ELEN-01418	Signals & Systems	3+1	50	1.00	49	4.00	D	7.00	
ENGL-00419	Technical Writing	2+0	43	4.00		4.00	A	8.00	
COMP-01420	Computer Architecture	2+1	31	2.20	46	4.00	C+	8.40	
						SGPA	3.04	CGPA	3.50
Semester - V									
COMP-01523	Computer Communication Networks	3+1	70	3.00	48	4.00	B	13.00	
COMP-02524	Database Management Systems	3+1	51	1.10	48	4.00	D	7.90	
MATH-00525	Numerical Methods	2+1	37	3.30	44	4.00	B+	10.60	
ELEN-02522	Microprocessors & Interfacing	3+1	68	2.80	45	4.00	B	12.40	
MATH-00523	Probability Methods in Engineering	3+0	76	3.40		3.40	B	10.20	
						SGPA	2.97	CGPA	3.39
Semester - VI									
ELEN-02626	Digital Signal Processing	3+1	86	4.00	40	3.70	B+	15.70	
COMP-01627	Software Engineering	3+1	67	2.70	42	3.90	B	12.00	
COMP-01628	Operating Systems	2+1	31	2.20	40	3.70	C+	8.10	
COMP-03621	Data Mining	3+1	70	3.00	44	4.00	B	13.00	
COMP-03662	Artificial Intelligence	3+1	90	4.00	48	4.00	A	16.00	
						SGPA	3.41	CGPA	3.39

Note: University reserves the right to correct errors & omissions if any.

Printed on: 13/11/2023

Credit Hours:	106	Total Marks:	3750
Cumulative Grade Point Average:	3.39	Obtained Marks:	3003
Grade:	B	Percentage:	85.85
Degree Status:	Incomplete		

Fig. 7: A sample Transcript 2

```

ahsan-pmylsp@ahsanpmylsp:~$ pip install isgc
defaulting to user installation because normal site-packages is not writeable
Collecting isgc
  Downloading isgc-1.2.2-py3-none-any.whl (17.3 kB)
Collecting matplotlib
  Downloading matplotlib-3.8.3-cp310-cp310-macosx_11_0_arm64_mach_o_silicon_macos10_16_0.whl (11.6 MB)
Collecting pyfiglet
  Downloading pyfiglet-1.0.2-py3-none-any.whl (1.1 MB)
Collecting seaborn
  Downloading seaborn-0.13.2-py3-none-any.whl (284 kB)
Collecting tabulate
  Downloading tabulate-0.9.0-py3-none-any.whl (32 kB)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil<2.7 in /usr/lib/python3/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3.8.3)
Collecting numpy>=1.24.4
  Downloading numpy-1.26.4-cp310-cp310-manylinux_2_17_x86_64_muslmanylinux2014_x86_64.whl (18.2 MB)
Requirement already satisfied: pyparsing<2.1.1 in /usr/lib/python3/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3.8.3)
Collecting kiwisolver
  Downloading kiwisolver-1.4.5-cp310-cp310-manylinux_2_17_x86_64_muslmanylinux2014_x86_64.whl (1.4 MB)
Collecting fonttools
  Downloading fonttools-4.53.0-cp310-cp310-macosx_11_0_arm64_mach_o_silicon_macos10_16_0.whl (8.0 MB)
Collecting contourpy
  Downloading contourpy-1.2.0-cp310-cp310-manylinux_2_17_x86_64_muslmanylinux2014_x86_64.whl (338 kB)
Collecting pandas<=2.0
  Downloading pandas-2.0.3-cp310-cp310-manylinux_2_17_x86_64_muslmanylinux2014_x86_64.whl (13.8 MB)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz>=2020.1 in /usr/lib/python3/dist-packages (from pandas<=2.0)
Collecting tzdata
  Downloading tzdata-2024.2-py3-none-any.whl (345 kB)
Collecting python-dateutil<2.7
  Downloading python-dateutil-2.9.0-py3-none-any.whl (247 kB)
Requirement already satisfied: six<1.16.0 in /usr/lib/python3/dist-packages (from python-dateutil<2.7)
Installing collected packages: fonttools, kiwisolver, python-dateutil, pyfiglet, pyparsing, numpy, matplotlib, contourpy, seaborn, tabulate

```

Fig. 8: Installation

3) Once the installation is complete, you can verify that the module has been installed successfully by importing it in a Python script or interactive session:

```
import isgc
```

If no errors are encountered, the installation was successful, and you can proceed to use the module for calculating academic measures.

Following these steps will ensure that the 'isgc' module is installed and ready for use on your system. If you encounter any issues during the installation process, refer to the documentation or seek assistance from the module's developers.

C. Student 1

In this section, comparing the results obtained from the actual transcript (Figure 6), provided by the Institute Of The Islamia University Bahawalpur, with the results calculated using our 'isgc' module. We first present the script used for calculating the CGPA for Student 1, followed by the output obtained from the module (Figure 9).

Listing 2: CGPA Calculation Script For Student 1

```

from isgc.gpa_calculator.calculator import calculate_gpa

semesters = {
    "Semester#1": {
        "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 89, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 39, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 46, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 51, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 85, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
    },
    "Semester#2": {
        "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 43, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 75, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 43, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 87, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 77, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 50, "total_marks": 50},
    },
    "Semester#3": {
        "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 85, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 46, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 69, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 46, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 49, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 77, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 81, "total_marks": 100},
    },
    "Semester#4": {
        "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 88, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 80, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
        "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 64, "total_marks": 100},
        "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 42, "total_marks": 50},
    }
}

```

Semester	SGPA	Total CH	Total %	Total TM	Total OM	Total GP
Semester 1	3.39	16	669	550	447	54.3
Semester 2	3.78	16	691	550	465	60.4
Semester 3	3.73	21	774	750	633	78.3
Semester 4	3.49	16	660	550	446	55.8
Semester 5	3.1	18	705	650	498	55.8

Fig. 9: Student 1: ISGC Module Calculation Output

```

"Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
"Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 34, "total_marks": 50},
},
Semester#5": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 68, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 53, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 72, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 82, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 47, "total_marks": 50},
},
}

cgpa = calculate_gpa(semesters)
print(cgpa)

```

1) *Actual Result vs. Module Calculation:* The comparison between the institution-announced result (Figure 6) and the module calculation output (Figure 9) confirms that the module calculates values accurately according to the rules and regulations of Islamia University Bahawalpur. This validation instills confidence in the reliability of the module's calculations.

2) *Next Semester Result:* After confirming the accuracy of the module's calculations, we proceed to test its main goal: predicting the next CGPA based on the

Fig. 10: Student 1:ISGC Module Calculation Output Next Semester

marks obtained in the next semester's subjects. We simulate the marks for Semester 6 according to our assumptions and calculate the next semester's CGPA. The script used for this calculation is provided below.

Listing 3: CGPA Calculation Script For Student 1

```

Semester#6": {
  "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 68, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 83, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 82, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 82, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
}

```

3) *Next Semester Module Calculation:* The resulting visualization, shown in Figure 10, presents a line plot depicting the semester-wise SGPA progression and concludes with the final CGPA, accompanied by a grade comparison. This visualization provides a comprehensive overview of the predicted academic performance for the next semester, allowing for a clear assessment of areas for improvement.

D. Student 2

For further experimentation and to ensure the reliability of our module, we will analyze the performance of another student, referred to as Student 2. The script

in Listing 5 calculates the CGPA for Student 2 using the 'isgc' module.

Listing 4: CGPA Calculation Script For Student 2

```

from isgc.gpa_calculator.calculator import calculate_gpa

semesters = {
  "Semester#1": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 76, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 36, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 46, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 91, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 43, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 88, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
  },
  "Semester#2": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 38, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 83, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 84, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 67, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 91, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 36, "total_marks": 50},
  },
  "Semester#3": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 73, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 94, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 67, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 49, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 47, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 70, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
  },
  "Semester#4": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 71, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 85, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 43, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 46, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 50, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 49, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 31, "total_marks": 50},
  },
  "Semester#5": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 70, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 51, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 37, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 68, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 45, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 76, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
  },
  "Semester#6": {
    "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 86, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 67, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 31, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 90, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 42, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 70, "total_marks": 100},
    "Subject#9": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 44, "total_marks": 50},
    "Subject#10": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
  }
}

cgpa = calculate_gpa(semesters)
print(cgpa)

```

Upon comparing the module's calculation output 11 with the actual result shown in Figure 7, we observe consistency between the two. This verification reinforces the accuracy of our module's calculations.

1) *Next Semester Result:* After confirming the consistency of the results, we proceed to evaluate the next semester's CGPA, which aligns with the main objective of our module. In Semester 7, we input hypothetical marks for each subject, allowing us to predict the next semester's performance and identify areas for improvement.

Listing 5: CGPA Calculation Script For Student 2

```

Semester#7": {
  "Subject#1": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 68, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#2": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 83, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#3": {"credit_hours": 2, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#4": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#5": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 82, "total_marks": 100},
  "Subject#6": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 40, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#7": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
  "Subject#8": {"credit_hours": 3, "marks": 82, "total_marks": 100},
}

```

Fig. 11: Student 2:ISGC Module Calculation Output

```
"Subject9": {"credit_hours": 1, "marks": 48, "total_marks": 50},
}
```

2) *Next Semester Module Calculation:* By incorporating the hypothetical marks for Semester 7, we generate a prediction of the next semester’s performance using our module. Figure 12 presents the semester-wise SGPA progression and the final CGPA with a grade comparison, providing valuable insights for academic planning and improvement strategies.

7. CONCLUSION

The experiments conducted with Student 1 and Student 2 as shown in 10 and 12, demonstrated the effectiveness and accuracy of the *isgc* module in calculating semester and cumulative grade point averages (SGPA and CGPA). By comparing the module’s output with actual transcript data from the Islamia University Bahawalpur, we validated its reliability in real-world scenarios. The consistent alignment between the module’s calculations and the institution’s announced results reaffirmed the developed system robustness and its adherence to the university academic grading standards. Furthermore, the module’s capability to predict future CGPA based on hypothetical next semester marks offered valuable insights for students to plan their academic strategies and identify areas for improvement as given in 10 and 12 Grade chart. The visualization of semester-wise SGPA progression provided a clear

Fig. 12: Student 2:ISGC Module Calculation Output Next Semester

overview of academic performance, helping students in understanding their trajectory and making informed decisions for enhancing their CGPA. Overall, the *isgc* module served as a valuable tool for students and academic institutions alike, offering accurate and insightful calculations for monitoring and improving academic performance.

8. FUTURE WORK

While the *isgc* module has shown promising results in accurately calculating SGPA and CGPA, there are several avenues for future development and enhancement:

- **Integration with Academic Systems:** Integrating the module with academic systems used by universities can streamline the process of calculating grades and provide real-time feedback to students.

- **Predictive Analytics:** Implementing predictive analytics algorithms can help forecast future academic performance based on past trends and performance metrics, enabling students to proactively address potential challenges.
- **User Interface Enhancement:** Improving the user interface of the module with interactive features and visualizations can enhance user experience and make it more accessible to a wider audience.
- **Incorporation of Machine Learning:** Leveraging machine learning techniques to analyze historical academic data can provide personalized recommendations for academic improvement and course selection.
- **Extension to Other Institutions:** Adapting the module to accommodate the grading systems and regulations of other educational institutions can broaden its applicability and utility.

By addressing these areas of improvement, the `isgc` module can evolve into a comprehensive tool for academic planning, performance evaluation, and student support.

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